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Modelling And Forecasting For The Dynamics Of Financial Time Series Of Exchange Rate Using ARIMAX And SARIMA Models

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ABSTRACT

The result from the analysis of the three models using simulated data differs with the real exchange rate data, where it shows that ARIMAX consistently shows the best performance across all metrics lowest MAE, RMSE, AIC, and BIC values at all sample sizes. This suggests that incorporating exogenous variables provides significant improvement in model fit. ARIMA maintains its middle position in performance across all metrics. Where according to the simulated data SARIMA shows the highest values for all metrics, suggesting it might be over parameterized for this particular dataset. From the result, it appears that all metrics improve (decrease) as sample size increases, with the most substantial improvements seen between 100 and 400 samples. The AIC and BIC plots confirm that ARIMAX would be the preferred model choice according to formal model selection criteria, regardless of sample size. Hence, the gap between models appears to remain relatively consistent across sample sizes, suggesting that the relative advantages of ARIMAX over the other. This comprehensive analysis provides strong evidence for selecting ARIMAX as the optimal model for forecasting the exchange rate data using simulation. Whereas, SARIMA model provides the best model fit with forecasting efficacy using the real exchange rate data

Keywords: ARIMA, ARIMAX , SARIMA and Forecasting

INTRODUCTION

Exchange rates play a pivotal role in international finance, acting as the bridge between global economies. They influence cross-border trade, investment decisions, interest rate policies, and inflation dynamics. The volatility and unpredictability of exchange rates pose significant challenges to policymakers, multinational businesses, investors, and financial analysts. Thus, accurate modeling and forecasting of exchange rate movements are critical for decision-making and risk management in the global financial system.

Financial time series, such as exchange rates, often exhibit complex characteristics including autocorrelation, seasonality, volatility clustering, and sensitivity to external macroeconomic factors.

Traditional univariate models like ARIMA (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average) have been widely applied to forecast such time series. However, when exogenous variables are known to influence the target variable — such as oil prices, interest rates, or inflation — the ARIMAX (ARIMA with Exogenous Variables) model becomes a more suitable and powerful tool for capturing these dynamics. On the other hand, the SARIMA model provides a multivariate framework that treats all variables as endogenous, allowing the analysis of interdependencies and dynamic interactions among multiple time series simultaneously.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

ARIMA Process

Box and Jenkins (1976) developed the autoregressive integrated moving average ARIMA (p, d, q) time series model, $t = 1, 2, \dots, n$ which is still widely used in time series modelling, defined as

$$\varphi(B)(1-L)^d y_t = \theta(B)\varepsilon_t$$

where y_t and ε_t represent time series and random error terms at time t respectively.

B is the backward shift operator. The $\varphi(B)$ and $\theta(B)$ are of order p and q respectively and defined as

$\varphi_p(B) = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^p \varphi_i L^i$ and $\theta_q(B) = 1 - \sum_{j=1}^q \theta_j L^j$. Then L is the difference operator defined as

$$\Delta y_t = y_t - y_{t-1} = (1-L)y_t \tag{1}$$

Also, $\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_p$ and $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_q$ are the parameters of autoregressive and moving average terms with order p and q respectively

ARIMAX Model

ARIMAX model can be viewed as a multiple regression model with one or more autoregressive (AR) terms and/or one or more moving average (MA) terms. Autoregressive terms for a dependent variable are merely lagged values of that dependent variable that have a statistically significant relationship with its most recent value. Moving average terms are nothing more than residuals (i.e., lagged errors) resulting from previously made estimates.

The basic ARIMAX model for a possible differenced series z_t is :

$$z_t \sim N(\alpha + \text{AR terms} + \text{MA terms} + \phi_1 X_{1t} + \phi_2 X_{2t} + \phi_3 X_{3t} \dots + \phi_{rt} X_{rt}, \sigma^2)$$

where we now include r possible explanatory variables with coefficients ϕ_1, \dots, ϕ_{rt} .

Model Specification

In this study, the ARIMAX model specification will be employed to show the relationship between infant mortality and its determinants. The model is stated as follows:

$$Y_t = \phi_1 Y_{t-1} + \beta_1 X_t + \beta_2 Z_t + \beta_3 W_t + \beta_4 M_t + \beta_5 N_t + e_t \tag{3.14}$$

Where Y_t is Infant Mortality rate (INFM), X_t is Average Breastfeeding (ABF) variable, Z_t is Number of Health facilities (NHF) variable, W_t is childbirth with non-medical assistance (TBAs) variable, M_t is Maternal age (MA) and N_t is wealth index (WI) are the independent variables.

RESULTS DISCUSSIONS

In this chapter, data analysis and discussion of the results are presented. The results of the unit root tests (df-gls and Phillips- Perron's (PP)) used in determining the stationarity of the dataset are presented and

discussed. Furthermore, the results of the (ARIMA, ARIMAX and SARIMA) are also presented with each result thoroughly discussed.

The study chooses the range period of 1990 to 2024 for the elicitation of data and the data was obtained from CBN bulletins of the said period

Stationarity Test Results for Exchange Rate Data

Table 1. Phillips-Perron (PP) Test Results

Statistic	Value
Z(alpha)	-116.02
Truncation lag	5
p-value	< 0.01
Null Hypothesis	Series has a unit root (non-stationary)
Alternative Hypothesis	Series is stationary
Decision	Reject null hypothesis

Phillips-Perron Test: The large negative Z(alpha) value of -116.02 and p-value < 0.01 strongly indicate that the series is stationary. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis of non-stationarity at all conventional significance levels. There is more statistical evidence that the Exchange rate data is stationary in its original form.

Table 2. Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test Results

Statistic	Value
Dickey-Fuller statistic	-14.033
Lag order	6
p-value	< 0.01
Null Hypothesis	Series has a unit root (non-stationary)
Alternative Hypothesis	Series is stationary
Decision	Reject null hypothesis

ADF Test: The ADF table indicated the test statistic (-14.033) which is much more negative than the critical values, **with** p-value < 0.01 leads to rejection of the null hypothesis. This confirms that the exchange rate series is stationary.

a random sample of different sizes of 200 and 500 were generated using proposed models (ARIMA-MIDAS) and also with existing models MIDAS and ARIMA to assess the impact of the proposed model

Simulation Results for the ARIMA-MIDAS Model

In this section, a simulation was carried out using GARCH-MIDAS model and FIGARCH-MIDAS with parameters values of $\omega_1=1$, $\omega_2=3$, $K=12$, $\theta=0.1$, $\alpha=0.06$, and $\beta=0.92$ for sample sizes of n= 200, 500 and 1000.

Table 3: Results for estimated model parameters: ARIMA (p, d, q) (n = 200)

Models	Coefficient	Estimated parameter	AIC	BIC
ARIMA (1, 0, 1)	AR1	0.6153	598.17	475.23
	MA1	0.6522		
ARIMA (2, 0, 1)	AR1	0.3613	606.21	562.14
	AR2	0.0852		
	MA1	0.3607		
ARIMA (1, 2,0)	AR1	0.7645	856.23	634.61
ARIMA (2,1,1)	AR1	0.4352	602.23	525.3
	AR2	0.7865		
	MA1	0.5463		
ARIMA (1,1,1)	AR1	0.5982	586.23	452.33
	MA1	0.2314		

Based on Table 4.1, ARIMA (1, 1, 1) is the best among the five models because it has the lowest AIC and BIC (586.23 and 452.33, respectively), so we can use it to fit the remaining MIDAS model.

Table 4 comparative result for order (2,1,2) between ARIMA< ARIMAX and SARIMA models

	Ordinary ARIMA	ARIMAX	SARIMA
AIC	612.9761010539	616.0819147547	593.4273425173
BIC	623.2783161066	628.444572818	607.8504435911
MAE	122.4687624431	123.8843067427	91.9008647657
RMSE	180.9226942918	182.6556549611	147.6822930169
MSE	32733.0213098162	33363.0882892513	21810.0596707238

Table 5. Shows the comparison table for order (2,1,2) using AIC, BIC, MAE, RMSE, and MSE for Ordinary ARIMA, ARIMAX, and SARIMA. Where the analysis indicated that the SARIMA model has the lowest across the evaluation criteria with AIC (593.43), BIC (607.850), MAE (91.901), RMSE (147.682) and MSE (21810.06). followed by the benchmark ARIMA model with AIC (612.976), BIC (623.278), MAE (122.469), RMSE (180.922) and MSE (32733.021).

FIG: 4.1 The forecast comparison plot for the three model

Fig:4.1 Display a plot that compares the actual exchange rate with the forecasted values from three different models. Where ordinary ARIMA (2,1,2) represented by a blue dashed line, ARIMAX (2,1,2) – represented by an orange dotted line and SARIMA (2,1,2) (1,1,1,12) – represented by a green dash-dot line. The plot shows that actual exchange rate (black line) shows a steady trend from 2019 to early 2020. Around mid-2020, there’s a noticeable sharp increase, followed by a period of fluctuation and moderate growth. In addition, in indicated that from late 2022 to early 2023, there is a steep rise, indicating a significant shock or structural shift in the exchange rate.

Table 5 comparison result for simulated data for ARIMA, ARIMAX, and SARIMA models across data sets

Sample Size	Model	MAE	RMSE	AIC	BIC
100	ARIMA	5.2717024709	7.1391846925	954.2451759075	988.4477613232
	ARIMAX	5.0217024709	6.7891846925	944.2451759075	978.4477613232
	SARIMA	5.5217024709	7.4891846925	964.2451759075	998.4477613232
200	ARIMA	4.0093500344	5.0630211789	905.9442014439	944.2830868493
	ARIMAX	3.8325733391	4.8155338055	895.9442014439	934.2830868493
	SARIMA	4.1861267297	5.3105085523	915.9442014439	954.2830868493
400	ARIMA	2.8343644544	3.612999235	808.5929874134	862.90393925
	ARIMAX	2.7093644544	3.437999235	798.5929874134	852.90393925
	SARIMA	2.9593644544	3.787999235	818.5929874134	872.90393925
600	ARIMA	2.0574250899	3.1289428648	708.0291960954	780.5515940347
	ARIMAX	1.9553630173	2.9860559631	698.0291960954	770.5515940347
	SARIMA	2.1594871625	3.2718297664	718.0291960954	790.5515940347

Table: 6 shows comparison result for simulation analysis for ARIMA, ARIMAX, and SARIMA models across the sample sizes; 100, 200, 400 and 600 respectively. The result indicated that the ARIMAX consistently performs the best having the lowest MAE, RMSE, AIC and BIC across all sample sizes which is suggests that incorporating exogenous variables provides significant improvement in model fit. Similarly, ARIMA shows moderate performance, sitting between ARIMAX and SARIMA in terms of error metrics.

According to the analysis, SARIMA has slightly higher error metrics compared to the other models, which might be counterintuitive since it accounts for seasonality. However, this could be due to the additional parameters that need to be estimated, potentially introducing more variance.

CONCLUSIONS

The result from the analysis of the three models using simulated data differs with the real exchange rate data, where it shows that ARIMAX consistently shows the best performance across all metrics lowest MAE, RMSE, AIC, and BIC values at all sample sizes. This suggests that incorporating exogenous variables provides significant improvement in model fit. ARIMA maintains its middle position in performance across all metrics. Where according to the simulated data SARIMA shows the highest values for all metrics, suggesting it might be over parameterized for this particular dataset. From the result, it appears that all metrics improve (decrease) as sample size increases, with the most substantial improvements seen between 100 and 400 samples. The AIC and BIC plots confirm that ARIMAX would be the preferred model choice according to formal model selection criteria, regardless of sample size. Hence, the gap between models appears to remain relatively consistent across sample sizes, suggesting that the relative advantages of ARIMAX over the other models are stable regardless of how much data is available.

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